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Nature-based solutions as more-than-human co- evolutionary technology: Basic concepts, theoretical framework and roadmap for practice

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1. Introduction

In this research report we develop the cross-disciplinary theory and practice of NbS as co-evolutionary technology. Following established terminological conventions, we use the term ‘cross-disciplinary’ as referring to collaboration among and conceptual and methodological integration across several established scientific disciplines, in our case mainly

- the sciences (biology, ecology),
- the social sciences (mainly sociology and economics) and
- the humanities (mainly anthropology, semiotics, and philosophy).

One challenge in conceptualizing NbS is that NbS design, implementation and practice involves a wide range of disciplines, reaching from biology to the humanities (Nesshöver et al., 2017). Different disciplines often suggest different stances in ‘doing’ an NbS: For example, engineering often suggests a technocratic approach, whereas sociology emphasizes participatory practices. Such disciplinary differences might be negotiated and reconciled in multi-disciplinary teams, yet we think that such work is facilitated if a shared cross-disciplinary framework is available. We include transdisciplinary approaches in our discussion of NbS practice, in general and in the context of Living Labs, although this report on theory does not directly engage authors with a non-scholarly background. Yet, we will argue that transdisciplinary knowledge co-creation in LLs is also essential for further developing the theory of NbS (Norström et al., 2020). We build on groundwork laid in a published paper that was background material to the original COEVOLVERS proposal (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2022) (summarized in section 2.1 of this report), which we modify, extend and complement in substantial and thorough ways.

In March 2022, the UNEA-5 agreed on the following definition of NbS:

“actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while

simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits.”

In practice, NbS are often adopted in an urban context (Kabisch et al., 2017; Sowińska-Świerkosz and García, 2022). Cities are shaped by human artefactual design and construction, mostly to the detriment of local ecosystems, which may even become artificial constructs themselves, such as urban parks. Since the share of humans living in urban environments is growing relentlessly, and since cities are the centres of human economic activity that drives global warming and environmental change, the role of NbS is especially important here (Hobbie and Grimm, 2020). This motivates our use of the term ‘technology’ in the first place: The NbS as a ‘solution’ is designed and implemented as a part of the urban techno-ecological system. Accordingly, there is a close connection with the concept of ‘green infrastructure’ which is defined by the European commission as

“A strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural areas with other environmental features, designed and managed to deliver a wide range of ecosystem services, while also enhancing biodiversity.”

Both NbS and GI are important elements of the European strategy aiming at the creation of sustainable societies to the benefit of humans and other living beings (Laforteza et al., 2018). Yet, even though strong affinity between the two concepts is well recognized, we notice that the discourses still lack conceptual integration, which we aim to achieve (Sowińska-Świerkosz and García, 2022) (for example, in the volume edited by Gomes Sant’Anna et al. (2023) only one chapter systematically combines the two concepts when dealing with GI in cities, even though the introduction clearly recognizes the close relationship). There is also ambiguity regarding other concepts, and which one is regarded as umbrella term (Ruangpan et al., 2020; Tzoulas et al., 2021).

Beyond such terminological issues, the discussion has also revealed that one potential drawback of both concepts of NbS and GI is to reproduce an instrumentalist and anthropocentric stance towards nature, which may jeopardize the claims that both should also contribute to biodiversity, hence implying a reciprocal relationship with nature (Maller, 2021; Ojeda et al., 2022; Welden et al., 2021). How to conceptualize

such a reciprocal relationship is a major theme of this report. We submit the claim that reciprocity between people and nature can be scientifically substantiated and made operational in conceptualizing NbS as *co-evolutionary technology*.

This report is divided into three main chapters. In chapter 2 we develop basic concepts of understanding NbS as more-than-human co-evolutionary technology in the context of Earth system sciences and introduce various meanings of co-evolution in relation to concepts such as co-creation. We further specify these meanings in suggesting a threefold conceptual framework of niche, infrastructure and landscape, in which we approach the co-evolutionary technology of NbS as multi-species niche construction. Chapter 3 elaborates on the theoretical foundations of these three key concepts to build the ground for perspectives on NbS practice which is the topic of chapter 4. In this chapter, we approach NbS multi-species niche construction as more-than-human infrastructural landscaping and introduce key aspects of this peculiar human activity.

2. Basic concepts

2.1. Levels of analysis

If we compare the two definitions of NbS and GI, the NbS definition focuses on ‘actions’ which seems broader than the definition of GI which refers to specific spatial and material forms. However, if we look at concrete lists of NbS comparing NbS to other types of solutions, it is salient that they are mostly seen as functional equivalents to technology, or, in reference to GI, to ‘grey infrastructure’ (for example, Hobbie and Grimm, 2020; Ruangpan et al., 2020). NbS as actions meeting the challenge of climate change in cities refer, for instance, to mangrove forests as alternatives to seawalls and dikes, tree canopy cover as alternative to building storm drainage facilities, or restored wetlands as alternative to water treatment. Indeed, the term ‘action’ seems too broad, as NbS by definition is ‘nature-based’: That means, actions are always engaging a material aspect of ‘nature’. For example, if I take the decision to turn vegetarian, that may count as pure action, but would not be seen as an NbS even if I wanted to reduce methane emissions to the atmosphere (Sowińska-Świerkosz and García, 2022).

Hence, our first step in recognizing NbS as technology is to approach them as *assemblages of actions and natural entities*, corresponding to assemblages of actions and human-made artefacts in conventional technology, and in fact, NbS mostly also include the latter as well. Such assemblages have been labelled as ‘naturecultures’ in the literature (Malone and Ovenden 2016).

Another aspect of comparing NbS and GI is the level of aggregation. We suggest distinguishing the *micro-*, *meso-* and the *macro-level* (Dopfer et al., 2004). NbS are mostly approached on the micro-level, such as a green roof, which is also defines the context of a Living Lab as a specific place, and which is suggested by the term ‘solution’ to a specific local problem. In comparison, GI is clearly conceptualized on the meso-level, such as a city (Ramyar et al., 2021). The micro- and the meso-level connect in considering topics such as upscaling an NbS (city-wide installation of green roofs) and creating connectivity among different NbS (such as green roofs and public parks). The macro-level refers to the first conceptual innovation that we introduced in our earlier paper: Situating the NbS in the context of the technosphere. This is the capstone in approaching NbS as technology, which is already salient in relating NbS and GI. We specify the notion of technology in terms of the notion of infrastructure, and approach infrastructure, on the global level, as the key element of the technosphere as a global phenomenon: Think of the network of global cities interconnected by transport and communication technologies, supported by vast infrastructures of food production and provisioning of other vital services of nature, such as water supply. The macro-level is where we ground our concept of co-evolution: We consider how evolutionary processes in the technosphere interact with evolution of the biosphere. In summary, see table 1.

	Material kind	NbS context	Example
Micro	Assemblage	NbS	Urban park
Meso	Network	Green infrastructure	Urban tree canopy
Macro	Sphere	Technosphere	Urbanization

Table 1: Levels of analysis

We specify the levels in terms of distinct material kinds: The assemblage, the network, and the sphere. So, a particular urban park is an assemblage of plants, animals and humans, all trees in a city build a network that defines urban canopy, and urbanisation is a global technospheric process in which NbS are situated, such as combining urbanization with rewilding as a general strategic approach.

In the macro-perspective, the Earth system sciences have adopted the view that in the transition to the Anthropocene, the technosphere has emerged as a new layer in Earth system dynamics and regulation (Donges et al., 2017; Haff, 2023), thus qualifying the Earth as a ‘hybrid planet’ in which technological artifacts play a partly autonomous evolutionary role (Frank et al., 2017). The notion of technosphere transcends technology as it highlights firstly, the systemic totality of the global network of technological artefacts, and secondly, its partial autonomy from human design (Haff, 2014a), hence manifesting distinct evolutionary processes, most basically driven by dissipation of energy, which interplay with geospheric and biospheric thermodynamic processes in the Earth system (Herrmann-Pillath, 2013; Kleidon, 2016). Given the sheer physical size of the technosphere, these effects have assumed geological dimensions, as manifest in the phenomenon of global warming or the omnipresence of artifacts (such as micro-plastics) all over the globe (Zalasiewicz et al., 2017). The manifestation of this is the growth of cities and urbanization which unfolds in spontaneous ways and is the key driver of economic growth and the ensuing consumption of energy and emissions (Batty, 2017; West, 2017).

We suggest enriching the ‘spheres’ approach by adding the ‘anthroposphere’, building on the original contributions by Vernadsky and followers who suggested notions such as the ‘noosphere’ to capture the distinct role of humans (Smil, 2003). The anthroposphere is the domain of human action as shaped by culture and institutions (‘second nature’) (Arendt, 2018). If we take anthroposphere and technosphere together, we arrive at the conclusion that the transition to the Anthropocene, this not yet fully formalized new geological epoch, means that the both spheres now encompass the biosphere in the sense that all biospheric phenomena have now become shaped by technological interventions, with the most universal one climate change, induced by humans, but also the pervasive presence of human made

artefacts all over the globe (Lenton et al., 2018). The latter goes beyond the scope of what has been labelled ‘anthromes’, which, however, already make up a very substantial share of the land mass of planet Earth (Ellis, 2011). Almost all NbS are located in anthromes.

Our general framework of NbS is depicted in figure 1 where the technosphere appears as encompassing regulatory layer of the hybrid planet Earth and the anthroposphere straddles biosphere and technosphere as humans are both, living beings and assemblages of bodies and technological artefacts (such as clothing, housing, smartphones etc.). Humans create NbS that belong to all three spheres but reach farther into the biosphere.

Figure 1: NbS in the Earth system framework

The three spheres are not separated from each other but overlap and interact in complex ways. Figure 2 visualizes this approach and shows how we can connect the micro- and the macro-level in the context of NbS in cities, which represent the meso-level. We can locate distinct forms of NbS in the different sections of the overlapping spheres.

There are biospheric phenomena in cities such as various forms of wildlife, for example, herbaceous plants (often so-called ‘weeds’) or wild animals searching for food (Barua and Sinha, 2022; Del Tredici, 2014). Organic urban gardening may be seen as interplay between anthroposphere and biosphere, not just because of the involvement of human action, but also the distinct cultural framing (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017). All three spheres intermingle in public parks, especially when informed by ideas of landscape ecology (Schenk, 2023; Waldheim, 2016). The biosphere retreats to the background when we consider public squares which might be almost devoid of greenery beyond decorative uses, but which come to life only by human public action, thus a cultural activity (Sennett, 2019). Finally, we might approach basic infrastructure such as the electric grid as being a part of the technosphere only, though being installed and operated by humans. Yet, for the vast majority of users this infrastructure is ‘invisible’, not engaging with them in direct action, and even the humans in charge may not be able to fully control the grid (Bennett, 2010).

Figure 2: Locating urban NBS in the three spheres

As we see, of the five examples considered here three count as NbS whereas the others count as ‘grey infrastructure’. However, we need to consider additional aspects.

As for the case for wildlife in cities, they would only count as NbS if human intentionality is involved, if only in allowing ‘wildening’ (Apfelbeck et al., 2020). For example, ‘weeds’ in the cracks of sidewalks may normally be cleaned up, but they might be given leeway if urban planners consider them to be means to cool down the microclimate: This would render ‘weeds’ as NbS (Prinz, 2023). On the other side, urban greenery certainly is grounded and constrained by grey infrastructure, as in the case of street greenery which contributes to using canopy as NbS for cooling and rainfall management (Vuckovic et al., 2023).

In our original approach to NbS we define NbS as human-designed technologies that mediate between technosphere and biosphere, thus assuming regulatory functions on the micro-level of NbS implementation (Figure 3). This is possible because NbS are both technological artifacts in the sense of being designed by humans according to some blueprint that aims to solve certain problems, say flooding of land adjacent to rivers, by means of engaging natural processes, such as creating wetland areas instead of building barriers and dams (‘sponge cities’). In this sense, NbS would appear as parts of the technosphere, similar to including, for example, poultry in industrialized chicken farms.

Figure 3: NBS as technology (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2022)

This observation reveals why the definition of NbS needs to be necessarily complemented by referring to co-evolution. The first sense in which we can further elaborate on the mediating role of NbS is to highlight the role of design (figure 4). In the design of urban infrastructure, this has been traditionally seen as focusing on the

‘grey’ elements which are conceived as being fully subject to human intention. An NbS is assuming a mediating role if the natural processes also impact on or are activated in the design of the urban infrastructure of which the NbS is a part. This means to harness the evolutionary capacity of nature. For example, when creating urban greenery, today a challenge is which plants may be better able to cope with climate change (Gulstrup et al., 2018; McDonnell and Haas, 2015). Human designers may leave leeway to spontaneous rewilding of greenery to discover the varieties that are better adapted to the new climatic conditions. This is one sense in which the NbS has co-evolutionary features that reach beyond human intention.

Figure 4: NbS design at the interface of biosphere and technosphere (modified, Herrmann-Pillath et al. 2022)

However, this approach remains anthropocentric as human needs stay at the centre. Our second published paper (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2023) pursues a different aspect of NbS as mediator which switches from an anthropocentric view to a eco(bio, geo)centric view. This is implied by the recognized demand that NbS should also contribute to biospheric needs, mostly specified in terms of the generic goal that NbS should contribute to biodiversity (IUCN, 2020). Despite this clearly accepted requirement, especially when crossing topical areas, such as switching from NbS to the GI context, biodiversity is named, but often, if not mostly marginalized

(Chatzimentor et al., 2020). There is a difference between considering the functions of biodiversity for human needs, such as resilience, and considering biodiversity as an independent goal (Filazzola et al., 2019). This aspect was already introduced in the first paper, so the second one presents an elaboration, especially regarding the consequences for implementing NbS as a practice. This orchestrates the move from the macro- to the micro-level.

The key problem has been already alluded to, namely that given the current rapid change of the planetary ecological conditions, human designers face limitations in planning the NbS for biodiversity, following the beacon of enhancing resilience (Malhi et al., 2020). Simply relying on past biodiversity, that is adopting a restorationist strategy, is doomed to fail (Thomas, 2020), which is, however, mostly emphasized in the NbS literature (Nehren et al., 2023). But ecological knowledge is also limited as far as future conditions are concerned. Hence, we suggest that the design of NbS must activate creative co-evolutionary potential beyond what had been argued previously, namely taking the needs and concerns of other species into full consideration, in the sense of recognizing multi-species creative agency (McDonnell and Hahs, 2015). We propose that is only possible in conceptualizing NbS design as artwork, in contrast to science-based engineering (Figure 5). NbS as artwork emphasize the creative projective powers that emerge in open interactions between human and non-human actors and highlights the role of aesthetics in enabling and sustaining transformative social dynamics. Elaborating on this idea grounds practice as discussed in chapter 4 on sound science.

Figure 5: Three types of NbS (diagram by Simo Sarkki, Herrmann-Pillath et al. 2023)

This new conceptualization of NbS requires to clarify conceptually the meanings of the different terms that we used without further definition so far, such as co-evolution and design. In the literature, this relates to various 'co'-concepts that we overview in the next section and propose a new systematic approach.

2.2. Co-evolution in relation to co-design, co-production and co-creation

In the discussion of NbS co-evolution does not stay at the centre so far, but notions such as co-creation and co-production. These often reflect different disciplinary backgrounds, such as, for example, co-production stemming from the discourse about public administration and management, where it means to engage users and citizens in the design and operations of public services (Voorberg et al., 2015). Clearly, this aspect is highly relevant for NbS as these are mostly installed by public agencies. Yet, in the context of sustainability 'co-creation' is invoked more often (Hirschnitz-Garbers, 2018). Both concepts do not include other living beings as agents of the NbS which is

emphasized by the notion of co-evolution advanced here. So, there is a need for conceptual clarification. We concentrate on four terms: Co-evolution, co-design, co-creation and co-production (figure 6).

The first step in our conceptual taxonomy is to distinguish between evolution and design, the most basic since Darwin developed the concept of evolution. This matters for discussing NbS, as seen, as we need to recognize that the knowledge base for NbS design is often incomplete and can only be created via evolutionary processes. We distinguish the concepts of evolution and design by the criterion of agency: Evolution is a non-agential process, design an agential one. However, once we consider the 'co', things get more complicated: Agency is an emergent phenomenon in evolutionary processes, and design relies on evolutionary generation of design knowledge. This mutual entanglement motivates the terminological extension by the 'co' in the domain of evolution. This refers to including various non-genetic forms of evolution, often referred to as 'cultural' (Boyd and Richerson 2008, Mesoudi 2011). Co-evolution also refers to the interplay of various trajectories of non-genetic evolution, such as technological and cultural. In reference to humans, this implies that there are endogenous forms of emergent agency, so that there is overlap with design, which is in turn conceptualized as co-design, similarly referring to forms of emergent agency that even engage genetic evolution, such as in the case of domestication of other species (Altman and Mesoudi 2019). Such areas of overlap are essential in considering NbS as co-evolutionary technology.

Figure 6: The conceptual fields of the four ‘co’s

In the literature, co-design is understood more narrowly as citizen participation in the design of a public service or other projects (Brandsen et al., 2018). So, our new approach differs substantially from conventional usage. In relating the two notions of evolution and design on the more fundamental level of evolutionary theory, we also need to consider various relationships between the three spheres.

By definition, design is excluded from the biosphere as approached since Darwin. However, co-evolution also applies for the other spheres and their interaction such that there is co-design which is also co-evolutionary, such as the cultural evolution of preferences over the design of gardens. The common understanding of co-design is non-evolutionary in this biospheric sense: This covers much of the public administration and management literature which approaches the public service as a non-evolutionary process which can be crafted by a process of inclusive deliberations among humans. Hence, the two conceptual fields overlap, but also remain distinct for many cases. In terms of spheres, co-design which is not evolutionary can only belong to the anthroposphere, thus excluding NbS which by definition extend to the biosphere and hence harness evolutionary processes.

As said, in the literature on co-production, co-design is sometimes seen as distinct from actually producing a certain public service. This applies for NbS as well, so that we need to distinguish the design stage from the stage in which the NbS is sustained. A fundamental fact about NbS is that in the latter stage there is always a necessary involvement of evolutionary processes in the biosphere, if the NbS also follows the norm to foster biodiversity. Hence, we suggest that we distinguish between the two notions of co-creation and co-production which can both involve co-evolution in the operational stage of NbS. The distinction between the two is that co-creation includes the more-than human dimension (which differs from common uses in the literature, e.g. Van Der Jagt et al. 2019), whereas co-production focuses on the human (which is also true for the NbS literature, see Raymond et al. 2017). In other words, co-creation extends beyond the anthroposphere, co-production stays within: But co-creation also includes the human, so the two concepts also overlap.

On the other hand, most processes of co-production are not co-creative as they exclude the biosphere. These distinctions matter for practical management of NbS, such as when implementing a stakeholder analysis that aims at designing inclusive design approaches (Hernandez-Santin et al., 2023). We could only consider human stakeholders, which would result in a co-production regime, or we could include non-human stakeholders, which, however, only would shift to co-creation if this also aims at inclusion in the process, and not just at targeting other species as beneficiaries. Hence, co-production can include co-evolution in the anthroposphere, but not necessarily co-creation. However, co-production is mostly not conceived as an evolutionary process and is seen as a way of participatory and deliberative knowledge production (Wyborn et al., 2019), as in this view it only engages human actors as intentional and reflexive agents. This judgment depends on how we approach co-evolution beyond the biosphere, such as when considering the role of culture in co-production (Soini and Dessein, 2016).

As said, co-evolution is a term that is used in various meanings as well, as it simply refers to the spontaneous coordination of change across at least two domains. For example, we may speak of co-evolution of technology and institutions, such as when new media allow for new forms of governance in society. In evolutionary economics

there is a sophisticated debate about the distinction between change and evolution that refers to the question how far change is conceptualized along Darwinian lines, with only this qualifying as ‘evolution’ (Hodgson and Knudsen, 2010). Ecological economics suggests a notion of co-evolution similar to the view championed here (Goddard et al., 2019; Kallis, 2007), which is also shared in sustainability science (Haider et al., 2021). We cannot discuss these questions in detail, but we will take a distinct stance, as we heed attention to the fact that the biological theory of evolution now includes significant deviations from the standard Neodarwinian paradigm, such as the theory of niche construction that we will deploy later. These also matter for how we conceptualize technological change as evolution (Arthur, 2009), which would apply for NbS as co-evolutionary technology.

The key point that remains valid for all variants of evolutionary theory is that the notion of ‘intelligent design’ is eschewed, hence reference to agency as guiding evolution. Co-evolution does not presuppose agency, as in the original Neodarwinian paradigm, but can include it. In principle, even when it comes to technological evolution, the role of agency is minimized in evolutionary models (Arthur, 2009), but this view is less relevant for us, as in practical contexts the long-term evolution of NbS does not matter directly, yet remains relevant for considering evolutionary potential. In the concept of co-evolutionary technology, the focus is on how the NbS interacts with evolutionary processes in both the human and the non-human domain. The question of temporal frames looms large, as the evolutionary clocks vary across species. In general, we would not consider genetic changes in humans as relevant, but probably of many insect species (Waring and Wood, 2021). So, in case of humans we focus on co-evolution of technology as NbS and culture, whereas for other species genetic evolution is more salient. However, as said, behavioural changes are also a driver of genetic evolution in many species, including the population level. Hence, cultural evolution also matters for certain species.

We suggest systematizing the various dimensions and meanings of co-evolution in reference to the three spheres (figure 7). In each of the areas of the three overlapping circles, we identify distinct co-evolutionary phenomena, at the centre of which stays

co-evolution across all three spheres which marks NbS as naturecultures and co-evolutionary technology.

Figure 7: Co-evolution across spheres

For better understanding, we supplement the diagram with table 2, with the pairing showing the 'co'. However, this table still overly reduces complexity as it should be in three dimensions, since in many cases we notice co-evolution of the three spheres simultaneously, though probably with different speeds. In table 2, we distinguish the columns and rows in terms of prime movers of co-evolution (row is prime mover). We present a further explanation in giving illustrations in NbS.

	biosphere	anthroposphere	technosphere
biosphere	Co-evolution of species in ecosystems	Co-evolution of humans and other species in domestication	Biospheric evolution impacts on agriculture as technology and vice versa
anthroposphere	Cultural change impacting on ecosystem change	Co-evolution of innovations and consumer habits	Culture change driving technological change that feeds back on culture
technosphere	Co-evolution of artefacts and behaviour of non-human species	Communication media co-evolve with cultural change	Co-evolution of AI and other technologies

Biosphere-biosphere: Co-evolution of NbS within the biosphere happens when intentional rewilding (such as allowing wild plant varieties to flourish in unexpected places (Soanes and Lentini, 2019), attracts other species who feed on those plants, thus further driving evolutionary changes without direct human engagement

Biosphere-anthroposphere: This case of co-evolution is classically represented by domestication, with different possibilities of which sphere is prime mover. For example, in the domestication of dogs there has been the view that humans have been prime movers, certainly when intentional breeding started, but for the early stages, dogs appear as prime movers (Gibson, 2021) which may also apply for feral dogs in cities today (Ragavan and Srivastava, 2020). We can conceptualize biosphere-anthroposphere co-evolution in many time scales and dimensions, such as genetic adaptations following the emergence of nomadic lifestyles (Bayless et al., 2017), but in the context of NbS cultural co-evolution is practically most relevant. This includes, for example, the change of aesthetic preferences in co-habiting with the species environment in the NbS, which feeds back on actions of care that sustain the NbS (Ávila, 2022).

Biosphere-technosphere: Biosphere-technosphere co-evolution emerges when artefacts such as certain obstacles to gene-flow via movements of animals influence further genetic evolution, which leads to the reverse conclusion for NbS design for biodiversity and evolutionary potential that would reduce such obstacles (Zhang et al., 2019). Genuine co-evolution of NbS happens if, for example, animal actions impact on the artefacts and induce changes (such as holes in fences which are not repaired anymore, while allowing plants to grow on the fence) (Del Tredici, 2014), with examples such as the rewilding of old industrial sites (Teixeira et al., 2021).

Anthroposphere-biosphere: Here, we have cases such as autonomous cultural changes in human societies which directly impact on biospheric evolution, such as the emergence of certain ideas about health uses of animal parts which drive their extinction. NbS sometimes need to overcome such co-evolutionary patterns when safeguarding biodiversity, such as tastes for certain forms of greenery (Saito, 2007).

Anthroposphere-anthroposphere: This includes a rich variety of phenomena of cultural co-evolution among different groups and strata in society via imitation and is the standard lore of the humanities, such as cultural studies. NbS often face the challenge that they might be seen

as eco-elitist fancies, especially if there are negative effects of groups that feel marginalized, as in the case of green gentrification (Anguelovski et al., 2022).

Anthroposphere-technosphere: Technological evolution is often driven by autonomous cultural changes which impact on user patterns, such as the case of the telephone which was pushed by communication needs in the rural areas of the US. Although this excludes NbS by definition, there can be important feedback on NbS if technological change counters certain effects that are expected from NbS.

Technosphere-biosphere: The case in point is climate change analysis. In the NbS context, one important topic is greening grey infrastructure by deliberately allowing for autonomous impacts of biotic phenomena on re-designing technology, including the case of learning from nature in design (Speck et al., 2022).

Technosphere-anthroposphere: One of the most important cases is the impact of communication media on culture and habits, such as social media. This can count for NbS, as technological change may open new forms of perceiving and interacting with nature (Bridle, 2022).

Technosphere-technosphere. This is a key aspect of technological evolution in general, such as the self-reinforcing dynamics of coal, steel, and steam engine. Today, an important phenomenon is the interaction between AI and other technologies. This can matter for NbS such as when AI enables the interpretation of animal signs and translating them into human media.

Table 2: Co-evolution across the spheres

In contrast to co-evolution, co-creation presupposes agency on part of individuals and groups, which may often require empowerment in the first step. Therefore, co-creation always involves ethical aspects, such as environmental justice concerns. This is well-established (Cousins, 2021). The tricky question is how co-creation can effectively include other species and generate knowledge regarding their affordances, agencies and capabilities, and in which way other species have or acquire agency and exercise their capabilities. Beyond agency, another difficult question is how far co-creation with other species, analogous to the human case, requires what kind of communication that transcends human language. We will discuss all these issues later in this report. As a summary, we present table 3 which compares the essentials of co-evolution versus co-creation. From now on, we focus on the two as we pay special attention to the more-than-human aspect of NbS.

	Co-creation	Co-evolution
Definition	Collaborative processes that lead into creation of new natureculture structures	Evolutionary processes leading to interlinked cultural and ecosystem change
Temporal scope	Short term time horizon	Long term open time horizon
Meaning of “co”	Collaboration by humans and non-humans	Co-evolution of biosphere and material culture / technology
Ethics	Who is included and who is not	No explicit ethical aspects
Type of potential	Collaborative potential	Evolutionary potential

Table 3: Co-creation and co-evolution (modified after Herrmann-Pillath et al. 2023).

2.3. The meso-level: NbS as niche construction

In applying our basic concepts on NbS, we suggest that the key analytical level is *meso*. This follows from the observation that the ultimate challenges that NbS are designed to meet are not located on the micro-level, in the sense of practical solutions to a specific problem at a specific place and time. Indeed, the challenges are macro, such as climate change and loss of biodiversity. To overcome the tension between the micro application and the macro challenges we need to think meso, that is in terms of larger, though not global contexts in which an NbS is implemented. For this, we need intermediate level theoretical concepts. We suggest the concepts of *niche*, *infrastructure* and *landscape*:

- The *niche* is a concept taken from biology, and points to the need for grounding NbS design and implementation in fields such as evolutionary ecology. More specifically, we refer to niche construction theory as recent theoretical alternative to standard Neodarwinism in biology (Odling-Smee et al., 2003).
- *Infrastructure* is conventionally associated with disciplines such as engineering and economics, though recently infrastructure research has been also pushed in areas such as anthropology. Here, infrastructure is approached in the more-than-human dimension (Barua, 2021), thus allowing for a new integrative view on NbS and GI.

- *Landscape* is a concept that closely relates to the humanities and creative practices, such as in landscape architecture, and that has itself been the object of cross-disciplinary approaches, since one relevant key discipline, geography, is multi-disciplinary, reaching from physical geography to cultural geography. We relate landscape to the Uexküllian notion of *Umwelt*, hence suggesting another way of integrating the more-than-human.

In this research report we aim at weaving together these multi-coloured strands into one coherent conceptual framework.

We overview our framework in figure 8. We conceptualize NbS as the activity of human niche construction. In doing so, we eschew the tendency in NbS literature and practice to focus on single NBS as ‘solutions’ to specific issues, say, planting trees in cities for cooling (Welden et al., 2021). We view single activities as ingredients of a whole range of human activities of constructing a niche for flourishing in a sustainable way. Niches are composed of many elements, including both NbS and non-NbS elements, such as the road flanked by trees as part of an urban settlement which in its totality defines the niche in which the residents live. We capture this comprehensive view by analysing the niche as ‘infrastructure’. As we will argue, following the recent transdisciplinary discourse on infrastructure (Barua, 2021; Howe et al., 2016), we approach infrastructure as encompassing both built and natural components, and we relate the ecological perspective of niche construction directly to infrastructure. This is what we refer to as ‘functional’ aspect of the niche. At the same time, we approach the niche as *Umwelt* in the sense of von Uexküll (Maran, 2020a). This highlights the semiotic, such as cultural or generally aesthetic aspects of the niche, which make the niche meaningful to human actors. Meaning is what motivates, generates and sustains niche construction activities, thus enacting the functions that define the niche ecologically. These semiotic dimensions are captured by the concept of ‘landscape’, which we develop as a more-than-human idea that combines ecological function with multi-species *Umwelten* (Kull, 2022).

Figure 8: Overview of conceptual framework

In this view, we specify the notion of ‘action’ in current definitions of NbS as the action of ‘niche construction’. In doing so, we reverse the direction of reasoning about the more-than-human, as we do not extend the analytical reach beyond the human, but move from the more-than-human to the human, such that the notion of ‘construction’ overcomes the nature / culture divide (Vogel, 2015). By implication, infrastructure is seen as constructing a niche, hence as an element of human ecology in terms of niche functions. This continues with the analytical reversal, which is completed in relating infrastructure to landscape. The landscape is the cultural form of the niche on the meso level. However, viewed from the perspective of niche construction, this raises the question how we can conceptualize NbS as elements of more-than-human landscapes. In the next chapter, we elaborate on these points in detail.

3. Basic theory

3.1. Niche construction

As a key notion, we refer to the concept of ‘niche construction’ (Kendal et al., 2011; Meneganzin et al., 2020; Odling-Smee et al., 2003). Extending the notion of niche construction to humans is not widely done, and mostly refers to early stages of civilization (Spengler, 2021). One reason is that in these contexts the notion of niche is mostly co-extensive with the size and reach of the human community, such as a pre-historical settlement and its surroundings (Rowley-Conwy and Layton, 2011). Even if a certain pattern of agricultural practices is shared in a larger population and extends across wider regions, their actualization remains mainly local and involves only sparse interactions beyond that niche. This is no more the case in modern human societies, especially when it comes to urban settlements: Via the division of labour on various scales, from regional to global, the life-sustaining processes reach far beyond the local environment. Urban settlements are deeply embedded into the technosphere with global scope, which therefore could be regarded as the human niche, including all biotic processes that are internalized, such as the banana production catering the nutritional needs of a Stockholm inhabitant (Haff, 2014b, Herrmann-Pillath, 2018).

However, despite these wide-ranging interactions, the local still matters in an essential way. This is salient if we introduce the distinction between the local environment and the *Umwelt*, sometimes also referred to as ‘semiotic niche’ in the biosemiotics literature (Hoffmeyer, 2009). In the niche-construction discourse, this connects with the notion of ‘cultural niche’ (Nagatsu et al., 2023; Shennan, 2011) which allows to distinguish between the physical spatial scope of a niche and the scope of the related cultural niche: That means, even if the physical niche of modern humans has vast extension, the *Umwelt* is still local.

Indeed, the dissociation of the two is one reason for our current ecological dilemmas, which also includes the fissures between human culture and non-human *Umwelts* (Maran, 2023). The human consumer of the banana does not directly experience the conditions in the banana producing places. In economics, this is treated as origin of ‘externalities’, that is, the actions of individuals as mediated by the contextual signs in

their local environment (such as the prices of bananas in the grocery) do not heed attention to physical-functional effects occurring elsewhere. Increasingly, these externalities feed back to the local, such as droughts and floods caused by climate change, and require local transitions to adaptive niche construction, for example, transforming the species composition of urban greenery and forests (Gulsrud et al., 2018). This brings the role of co-evolution in shaping the human niche to the fore even in an urban context, which has been mostly confined to the context of agriculture so far (Altman and Mesoudi, 2019; Haider et al., 2021).

When relating this discussion to NbS, following our distinction of levels of analysis, most NbS operate on the micro-level, partly on the meso-level, but do not affect the macro-level directly. This implies that they are embedded into the *Umwelt* but may be only marginally affecting the human niche as shaped by the technosphere. Hence, there is the possibility that an NbS does not affect the larger pattern of externalities that drive macro-processes like climate change (important exceptions include carbon sequestration by forests, Seddon et al., 2020).

Indeed, most NbS are promoted as measures of local adaptation to climate change, but not as measures of mitigation (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change IPCC, 2023, p. 948ff). As such, they have the same function as conventional technologies. Consider the case of urban heat islands: They do not contribute to global warming directly, as this is exclusively driven by the greenhouse effect (Kleidon et al., 2023). Yet, the impact of global warming on human health is reinforced in such local contexts. A standard ‘grey’ solution is air-conditioning, which, however, leverages energy consumptions and hence emissions, if not fully powered by renewables (figure 9a). A self-reinforcing mechanism emerges where heat islands eventually affect global warming via adaptation by humans (and not via direct physical heat transfers). Implementing an alternative NbS as co-evolutionary technology establishes another possible connection between micro- and macro-level, because firstly, evolutionary novelty can change trajectories of larger patterns of evolutionary change across domains, such as new species variants or new cultural habits, and secondly, such novelties may diffuse across the boundaries of the local, ultimately even affecting the original externality (figure 9b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 9a, b: Adaptation in local (micro) and global (macro) scales: Conventional technology versus NbS

In the biological concept of niche, we need to distinguish between the species level and the individual level, which is important for conceptualizing the ‘local’: The biological ‘niche’ is often conceived as a ‘type’ relating to the species as a ‘type’ which then defines species-specific, though generic properties of the niche as type realized in a variety of local tokens. The biological niche is the set of potential resources of the environment, in the broadest sense, that is occupied by a species for survival and reproduction. We must distinguish between actualized and potential uses of

resources. Darwinian theory suggests that competition and selection will drive species evolution to exhaust all potential resources: In economic parlance, evolution is a 'discovery process' in which living systems thrive towards using all potentially available resources. This discovery process unfolds via individual variation subject to selection, reproduction of new variants and retention of adaptive features. The important question is to which extent this individual variability among local populations is only running via the genetic channel, or whether there are also behavioural variations that are transmitted non-genetically. This distinction is important when considering creativity in niche construction: For example, individual animals can be creative in exploiting resources offered by human settlements. Behavioural innovation, including imitation and learning in populations, is an important mechanism of speciation (often, though controversially, referred to as 'Baldwin effect').

Behavioural innovation in a local context is a key mechanism that drives evolution in niches that are artificially created by humans (McDonnell and Hahs, 2015). In considering biodiversity, we need to include the multiplicity of niches that connect physical-functionally with a given element of material infrastructure, and which often remain distinctly local. Take the example of falcons in New York city: When the Empire State Building was built, architects did not design for falcons, yet, the building proved to be an inviting habitat for falcons preying on other species of the urban lifeworld, such as rats. This is a case in point for the creativity of co-evolution between human artefacts and other species adaptive strategies, which is mediated via what has been dubbed 'semiotic co-option': The building creates semiotically mediated affordances for innovative animal behaviour (Maran and Kleisner, 2010). This can result in even genetically localized populations, as in the case of urban feral pigeons. So, human niche construction is inextricably enmeshed with niche construction by other species, and for this we also posit the duality of physical functionality and *Umwelt*, the latter understood as plurality of *Umwelten* in a local pattern of multi-species co-habitation. Hence, the *Umwelt* mediates between the local and the general, the individual and the species, or generally, tokens and types in evolution.

Figure 10: Species and individuals in niche construction

As we see, for our argument it is essential to distinguish neatly between different levels of analysis (Trappes et al., 2022) (figure 10). This corresponds to our previous distinction between micro, meso and macro-level. The concept of niche relates to the population level where evolutionary changes unfold, hence the formation of species as types. Niche construction operates on the individual level, as this is an activity located in time and space. However, the meaning of ‘individual’ is ambiguous here because this can also be understood in a generic way, hence as a type: If we approach the population as a statistical distribution of individual variants, the individual in this sense is one value in the distribution. Therefore, we distinguish between two aspects of the individual. One distinction is between the individual and the population level in a typological sense: For example, the evolution of beavers unfolds on the population level, but building dams as niche construction is individual level, though in a typological sense. Yet, on the other hand, this activity is necessarily individualized in terms of tokens, that is, specific individuals of beavers buildings dams at a specific location and time.

Referring to the micro-, meso- and macro-distinction, we notice that in biological evolution the macro-level is only relevant as a theoretical construct of a generic

concept of population relating to a generic concept of niche. The reason is that evolutionary change can only be causally mediated on the meso-level, hence realized population patterns in specific local manifestations of the niche. Even if migratory species may live in widely distant places at various stages of organismic development, such as eels, this does not mean that the niche is defined by that spatial reach (eels move from niche to niche in different developmental stages). This reveals the special nature of the human niche as shaped by the technosphere, which means that even humans who do not move beyond their local *Umwelt* still may rely on resources at distant places. The technosphere is not 'abstract' but classifies as a 'hyperobject' ontologically (Morton, 2013). This status is one of the crucial epistemological obstacles to understanding global phenomena such as climate change in terms of the human *Lebenswelt* as *Umwelt*. This also creates major theoretical challenges for conceptualizing NbS.

The micro-level is crucial to diagnose genuine individual creativity and agency in evolution. For conceptual clarity, we suggest distinguishing between the 'niche' and the 'habitat', the latter being understood as the token of a niche (Trappes et al. 2022 refer to this as 'realized individual niche'). Niche construction ultimately is only manifest as habitat level activity, which therefore includes a wide variety of behaviours. As figure 10 shows, this results in a circular closure of the evolutionary process, as constructed niches become forces of selection, which is formally analogous to figure 9. Subsequently, we will relate the notion of habitat to the concept of 'landscape'. The habitat as a specific location relates to the human niche, but as a physical setting it is also the location where all other co-habiting species interact with human niche construction. Even highly artificial human habitats such as cities offer vast opportunities for creative niche discovery by all other species (Parris et al., 2018; Rivkin et al., 2019).

Niche construction only appropriates certain environmental resources or better, specific uses of these resources, such that diverse niches can co-exist within one spatial segment, thus resulting in local biodiversity. This implies a twofold process of exhausting the potential of a spatial segment of the environment, intra- and interspecies competition, implying that depending on the richness of potential

resources there is more or less space for niche expansion and multiplication. The concept of 'resource' in the broadest sense includes other living systems, both in the sense of prey and of products that they generate ('waste', like excrements). Therefore, the niche evolves endogenously in interaction with other niches, hence is not a fixed given as physical environment. Theoretically, niche expansion is only limited by the availability of energy, yet there are structural constraints resulting from the realized forms of diverse organismic metabolisms in a given spatial segment. For example, even the extremely diverse ecosystems of the Amazonas rain forest are constrained by the availability of phosphorus.

Niche construction results in a major re-conceptualization of evolutionary theory, for two reasons (Odling-Smee et al., 2003).

First, the transformation of the environment means that the latter is no longer an independent force of selection, as the living system itself alters this force. However, the question arises whether this is a special case at all, as all living systems alter the environment by their actions, in particular, by their excrements and debris after death and decay. This changes the niches of other living systems, which in turn impacts on other niches. Considering this, an ecosystem can be conceptualized as a large distributed system of synergetic niche construction over time and space: We refer to this as 'co-evolution'. Hence, the concept of niche construction should distinguish two different, though related meanings, namely the transformation of the environment by 'construction', and the more specific meaning of 'building'. Independent from which meaning is used, the general point remains true that the niche is endogenous to the activity of the living system. The distinctive feature of *building* a niche is that there is a specific behavioural pattern involving agency which excludes, for example, reefs made by corals, or Darwin's much-cited earthworms and the soil, which still qualify as niche construction. However, this is a complex matter, as the question is whether agency can be distributed in populations of agents, the archetypical case is the stigmergic construction of termite mounds (Hansell, 2007), compared to nest-building by birds which can involve genuine agency of individuals (Prum, 2017). These distinctions are important when considering the possibility that human niche building as NbS would also aim at supporting non-human niche construction, which is familiar from activities

such as composting (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017) or constructing bird houses (Parker et al., 2022a).

Second, this has a major implication for evolutionary theory since we can no longer reduce biological heredity to the genetic level. Endogenous niches include channels of non-genetic heredity, especially if the products of construction persist at a time scale longer than the reproductive cycle. This is evident when we consider the phenotype. In classical Neodarwinian theory, the phenotype is exclusively determined genetically. This can include the 'extended phenotype', such as the nest of a bird if nest building is genetically prescribed and enabled (Dawkins, 1999). But if the niche is altered such that descendants also inherit that niche, the niche also determines the phenotype since behaviour will adapt to it even without being genetically determined. That means, there are at least two channels by which the constructed niche is endogenous: First, in the longer run, the genetic endowment may embody the niche in terms of specific adaptations, and second, the constructed niche determines behaviour in the developmental dimension.

This discussion reveals that for niche construction it is not necessary, as mostly assumed in the biological literature, that the process includes genetic co-evolution, since what counts is heritability of phenotypical characteristics via the interaction between the constructed niche and behaviour. This is important for our context as we do not refer to the genetic longer run explicitly, though not excluding it. More specifically, we include genetic aspects in our discussion of biodiversity, but not in reference to humans, since this would require considering time scales beyond centuries. Yet, in principle human niche construction involves genetic evolution as well (such as long run effects of medicine and pharmacology on the genetically endowed immune system) (Gluckman et al., 2020). In case of humans, cultural co-evolution matters more.

We summarize niche construction theory in figure 11. Contrary to naïve selectionism, behaviour and environment are seen as co-evolving, via niche construction as a specific mechanism that endogenizes the environment. This implies that selection and heredity do not only operate via the genotype, but also via the phenotype directly,

since behavioural creativity changes the context of selection, and because the constructed niche channels phenotypical expressions directly.

Figure 11: Basic conceptual structure of niche construction

Further specifying the phenotypical channel, we enhance the concept of ‘niche’ by considering its semiotic dimensions. The distinction between physical environment and niche is stated clearly in von Uexküll’s distinction of ‘Umgebung’ and ‘Umwelt’ (Maran, 2020a; Uexküll and Kriszat, 1934). On first sight, *Umwelt* seems synonymous with niche, as both concepts are centred on the species and its relationship with the environment. However, there is fundamental methodological difference. The niche is conventionally analysed in terms of a third-person observer perspective, that is, ecological analysis based on biological knowledge about organisms and their physical interactions with the external environment. The *Umwelt* is how this environment appears to the living systems, hence is a semiotic construct in the ‘first person’ perspective of the system. Its relationship to the niche is manifest in the behaviour of the living system, i.e., its actions, which result in feedbacks on internal organismic states. The key concept that connects the notions of niche and *Umwelt* methodologically is ‘affordance’ (Chong and Proctor, 2020; Cisek, 2007): On the one hand, affordances are physical givens of the environment, on the other hand, they are relative to the capacities of the living system, with the link being established via semiotic processes. We summarize this in figure 12.

Figure 12: Niche and *Umwelt*

The force of selection in figure 11 relates to the notion of ‘function’ in figure 12, in the sense of adaptation to the niche. Functions can be broad (such as reproduction) or narrow (such as moving in space), and their realization results in niche construction. The behaviour that generates the functions is elicited by affordances that are manifest in the environment but relate to the capacities of organisms to realize functions. Hence, affordances and functions are intrinsically related.

Affordances relate both to genetically endowed behavioural capacities and to flexible behavioural variations. We can view affordances as ‘sense making’ enacted by the organism which is crucial when we consider the behaviour in changing and novel environments: Affordances are embodied in the organism such that a new environment is interpreted in the light of past experiences, and hence the organism enacts them in this environment, thereby creating a new niche which is functionally equivalent to the old niche (such as rock pigeons moving from cliffs to urban settlements). This enables behavioural innovation and flexibility in most living systems

independent from genetic endowments, down to the level of the individual (Rabdeau et al., 2021). As shown in figure 12, the duality of niche and *Umwelt* implies the duality of two evolutionary forces, one is selection, that is the standard concept of the Neodarwinian synthesis, the other is creation that operates in non-genetic media, often generically referred to as 'culture', whereas we relate this to the semiotics of evolution (Hoffmeyer, 2009; Wheeler, 2006). Referring back to our earlier discussion, we relate the functional analysis to the type and the *Umwelt* to the local, i.e., as token. Affordances are not abstract functions, but concrete potentials in a specific local environment. As in the original Gibsonian meaning, they are not 'subjective', but are properties of the material environment. Overcoming the debates in psychology about the meaning of this concept (Scarantino, 2003), we argue that affordances are a prime example of 'intra-action' in the sense of Karen Barad (2007). Methodologically, this means that the corresponding notion of agency is approached as being distributed between agent and environment (Malafouris, 2013). This allows to overcome dualistic views on agency that separate the human from the biotic world, and to define a more-than-human concept of action, which is essential for NbS practice as elaborated in chapter 4.

One concept that covers these intricacies is the eco-field hypothesis (Farina, 2012; Farina and Belgrano, 2006). The eco-field can be conceived as a specification of the general concept of affordance in the context of niche analysis. An eco-field establishes an interaction between certain properties of the environment and an organismic function that is semiotically mediated. That means, an organism relates with the environment via many eco-fields, such as an eco-field relating to foraging or an eco-field relating to predation and so on, resulting in a spatially complex structure since the environmental features can have different scope and scale: For example, the foraging eco-field of a rodent will be focused on the closer environment on the ground, whereas the eco-field for predation may also refer to the sky and signs of predatory birds. The totality of eco-fields defines the *Umwelt* of the organism. This is distinct from the niche, such that the relationship between organismic function and niche resources, conceived as behaviour guided by the eco-field, can fail to actualize this relationship: for example, the animal may expect resource access, given certain environmental

signs, but eventually this is a mistake. On the other hand, there is also potential for discovery and learning.

The distinction between the physical-functional aspect of the niche and its semiotic aspects is familiar from other scientific discourses, of which is especially relevant the distinction between 'space' and 'place', with the latter referring to the many ways how people refer to a location cognitively, emotionally and in their everyday practices (Tuan, 2011). We suggest the concept of 'aesthetics' to refer to these various approaches as an umbrella term, interpreted in terms of John Dewey's approach to aesthetics as experience (Dewey, 2013; Leddy and Puolakka, 2021).

In the following, we will relate this to the notion of 'landscape': Theories related to evolution, ecology and landscape emphasise the concept of 'affordance landscape' that goes beyond an adaptive landscape (Heras-Escribano & De Pinedo-García, 2018). Both 'niche construction' and 'landscape affordance' theories consider the mutual shaping and mutual constitution of organisms in their environment, which may support the notion that 'niche construction' can be viewed as an evolutionary process involving the construction of affordances by organisms (humans and other species). Experiences result from various landscape affordance potentials, such as physical, functional, cognitive, and sensory, and are facilitated by both visual (conditions and quality) and non-visual (e.g., olfactory experiences) stimuli (Mishra et al., 2020). In a nutshell, we explore the aesthetic dimension of niche construction as a key aspect of 'doing' an NbS, tying up with recent development in combining ecology and urban design (Corner and Hirsch, 2014). The conceptual bridge to our model is to relate the notion of habitat to the notion of 'landscape'. But before we can achieve this, we need to clarify the concept of infrastructure in relation to niche construction.

3.2. Infrastructure

Infrastructure is a topic that has been less discussed in the social sciences and the humanities, mainly left to civil engineering and related sciences (Josa and Aguado, 2019). However, in the past two decades infrastructure has increasingly received attention by sociologists and anthropologists who focus on aspects far beyond the

merely physical (Anand et al., 2018; Howe et al., 2016). Among the aspects most relevant in the current context are: The relationship between infrastructure and social structures of power and stratification, the role of non-built elements in infrastructure, including both other species and people, or the shaping of attitudes and habitus by infrastructure. Often, this research is foundational in the sense of questioning even basic concepts in the social sciences and the humanities, most notably, the notion of agency (Bennett, 2010): this includes both the idea of material agency of physical infrastructure and the concept of agency distributed in assemblages of actors and things (Perrotti, 2022). For analysing such constellations, new theoretical resources are mobilized, such as actor-network theory (Latour, 2005) or practice theory (Voß et al., 2023).

Taken together, these approaches do no longer reduce infrastructure to the notion of built physical structures. All these conceptions converge on the idea to overcome false dualities (nature/culture, natural/artificial, human/non-human) and taking as a unit of analysis holistic, while specifically materialized phenomena. For example, a practice relates to various constituent elements such as human agents, artefacts and processes unfolding in time, such as driving to work every morning. As we will see, this is the key for linking our theoretical work with applications discussed in chapter 4: Designing NbS as co-evolutionary technology does not mean to set up certain physical and ecological functions, but eliciting and sustaining certain practices linked to material patterns and manifest behaviours: This provides the theoretical grounding for the 'official' definition of NbS as actions that we introduced at the beginning. In this practice focus, NbS design is necessarily 'local' as approached in the previous chapter.

Infrastructure is most relevant when it comes to the question how human niche construction is situated in the concert of multi-species niche construction (for rich illustrations, see Tsing et al. 2020). Most human built infrastructure has a direct negative impact on other species because it competes for space and resources often in an exclusive way: Building a highway makes that part of the ground inaccessible to almost any other form of life and may jeopardize mobility of other living systems. Accordingly, in understanding multi-species niche construction the interaction between human and other species niches is essential, and the focus must be on

infrastructure. At the same time, given the recent theoretical advances, we can also generalize the notion of infrastructure to be included in the concept of niche: To a large extent, the niche is a kind of infrastructure. This is obvious once we distinguish between infrastructure as a stock and the flow of actions enabled by that stock that mobilize certain resources in the niche. For example, a highway is a stock that enables transportation. Similarly, a tropical forest is a stock that generates a wider range of ecosystem services to all members of the local ecosystem. This allows to define green infrastructure as an assemblage of built ‘grey’ infrastructure that includes biotic capacity to generate ecosystem services (figure 13). This parallelism is also salient in the concept of ‘nature capital’ (Costanza, 2023), thus directly relating built capital with ecosystems. Indeed, the precursor to the term ‘green infrastructure’ was ‘ecological infrastructure’ (Silva and Wheeler, 2017). In fact, the notion of GI is pertinent in our current context, but the notion of ‘nature as infrastructure’ is much wider (Carse, 2012).

Figure 13: Green infrastructure as assemblage of built and biotic elements

In this conceptual extension, one difficulty is to distinguish between the niche as infrastructure and the niche as a set of resources (figure 14). We suggest that this difference can be pinned down to the relationship with agency: A resource is what actions aim at, whereas infrastructure enables this action. There is also a conceptual connection to capital: Infrastructure extends over a longer time span than action: The

highway lasts longer than the driving, or the tree lasts longer than the bird's perching on a branch. Finally, and most importantly, we can conceive infrastructure as an assemblage of affordances, which highlights the close enmeshment of its material properties and related forms of agency that we explore now. Hence, we need to distinguish between niche and *Umwelt* in analysing infrastructure, and the functions that realize certain objectives of actions.

Figure 14: Niche and infrastructure

The relationship between infrastructure and action is complex, as infrastructure is an element of agency which blurs the line between the subject of action and its material enabler, which qualifies action as practice (Nagatsu et al., 2023). This is important because this also implies for human niche construction that we can no longer neatly distinguish between built infrastructure and 'nature', if only because humans as living beings are also part of the infrastructure. This is straightforward to recognize if we think of unused infrastructure: Ruins of infrastructure are no infrastructure at all, like a corpse which is no more a living being.

This is salient when we consider the conceptual vagueness of niche construction again (Spengler, 2021), which, if we refer to humans, may eventually include all kinds of

environmental impacts of humans, hence today even the entire Earth system as the human niche and considering the biosphere as subordinate to the technosphere (Herrmann-Pillath, 2018). In this view, there is no 'nature' anymore as separate ontological domain (Vogel, 2015). However, following Vogel, we may define 'nature' as being the domain of the uncontrollable and the unpredictable. Then, infrastructure may obtain the status of 'nature' since most infrastructure comes close to being an 'hyperobject' (Morton, 2013) in transcending human capacities of control and even epistemic reach (corresponding to Haff's principles of technosphere analysis (Haff, 2014c)). Think of the international trade network that centres on the artefact of the container: This includes harbours, ships, lorries, trains etc. in a truly gigantic and globe spanning infrastructure. No human has ever designed this infrastructure from scratch, but it has emerged from market actions undergirded by public policies of many governments without coordination. Many infrastructure projects, even on smaller scaler, still have the status of 'megaprojects' that create distinct challenges to human design and control (Flyvbjerg, 2014). In this sense, infrastructure obtains the status of 'nature'. Then, it is straightforward to conceptualize infrastructure as a hybrid, or 'natureculture' (Malone and Ovenden, 2016). We can elaborate on this in two different ways.

One is that there is literally a constant struggle between the technological artefact and biospheric entities over controlling the space: Think of ubiquitous herbaceous plants that easily occupy the tiniest holes and cracks in built objects like a street. Humans need to invest effort, and often with strongly negative environmental impacts, to drive away all other forms of life from the space occupied by an infrastructural artefact (and harming their own health, as in the infamous case of Roundup). Since infrastructure is long-living and is itself subject to forces of erosion originating in the geophysical environment, there are many forms how infrastructure is eventually re-integrated in the biosphere, most visible in industrial ruins re-appropriated by fauna and flora (Jasper, 2020; Teixeira et al., 2021) but also in operating infrastructure, such as solar parks (Uldrijan et al., 2022). All infrastructure in use offers niches for other living systems who adapt to this artefact (think of rats living in the sewers). Often this creates potential of conflict between humans and other living beings (such as scorpions

entering the bathroom via the sink; Ávila, 2022). Therefore, we can speak of co-evolutionary more-than human niche construction which, however, has been ignored as a fact by humans so far, or was only seen as a nuisance. Reversing this tendency offers huge co-evolutionary potential: One example is greening the car-parks which are ubiquitous in all cities (Evans and Hardman, 2023). Interestingly, this includes forms of co-production via the market, if owners charge higher fees for greening and tending, and customers endorse this. In contrast, the notion of GI is not necessarily extended to the more-than-human, in the sense of mainly referring the notion of ecosystem services to the human (Derby Lewis et al., 2019).

The other meaning of infrastructure as natureculture is salient once we consider humans as part of the biosphere, living beings, after all. This opens the vista for envisaging humans like the scorpions adapting to the infrastructure. In this case, natureculture refers to the behavioural adaptation of humans to the environment as shaped by the infrastructure. This corresponds to the co-evolutionary view on niche construction. As elaborated in chapter 2, the meaning of co-evolution is manifold and does not only refer to gene-culture co-evolution. Within the human domain, we can speak of co-evolution in many ways, such as of institutions and technology: For example, highly centralized political systems tend to adopt large-scale infrastructural projects which in turn undergird centralized power in their management.

So, in sum, infrastructure is a co-evolutionary phenomenon of its own status. One important topic illustrates the connection between these two aspects, namely when deficient infrastructure is considered. Anthropologists have argued that in such cases people become parts of infrastructure since the uses are mediated and enabled by their regular social interactions, in the sense of social capital complementing the built infrastructure, such as when people in need for water arrange irregular ways to access the public water supply (Simone, 2008). For our unfolding argument, the case is even more important when other species assume direct infrastructural roles (Barua, 2020). This is insinuated by the notion of 'green infrastructure', which, however, still means that this is built infrastructure (hence, niche building). We refer here to co-evolutionary constellations: For example, in Egypt urban pigs play an essential role in waste processing which became evident when hundreds of thousands of them were culled

in a swine flu epidemic, resulting in the immediate piling up of wastes. As we will show in our section on applications, this is a case of a non-intended coevolution, whereas in the case of an NbS, such infrastructural symbiosis is intended, such as deploying goats in fire protection who keep inflammable scrubs down (Pareja et al., 2020).

Let us look at the coevolution of human agency and infrastructure in some more detail, Infrastructure as a complex collection of artefacts has certain properties which shape such co-evolutionary phenomena (Star, 1999). Infrastructure is often almost invisible or ‘transparent’, which means that people often use it without realising it, such as when taking a shower, we do not remind ourselves of the vast system of water supply and heating that supports it. Transparency indicates a significant co-evolutionary mechanism: We adapt our behaviour to the infrastructure, even rationally, when considering costs and benefits of potential actions. Most significantly, we adopt habits that are supported by the infrastructure: The artefact comes to life via practices. As in the example of the shower, the transparent and efficient availability of hot water at all times fosters the emergence of a culture of hygiene and leisure that combines with other activities, such as using shower creams and so on. We become aware of this adaptation via internalisation when the water supply breaks down, and we do not feel well without our regular hygienic procedures.

Since the infrastructure must be clearly distinguished from the flow of actions, there is a difference between local and global efficiency of actions. The theoretical notion that comes to the forefront is path dependency, which is a key concept in economics that highlights the evolutionary nature of infrastructure and technology in general (Arthur, 2009): Once a certain infrastructure is set up, it becomes increasingly difficult to alter the direction of further changes since the costs of running actions are lower than the costs of alternative actions that would require setting up a new and different infrastructure. Path dependency is conditioned by many factors: One is habit formation, and another is the fact that infrastructure grows mainly via a combination of continuous repairing and fractal expansion (like a road network) (Batty, 2017). Consequently, in human societies we often observe the competition between alternative infrastructural regimes, which represent different paths, and where global efficiency might favour one path, yet, locally bound and contextualized decisions may

favour the less efficient alternative. The paradigmatic example is the competition between the car and the train as transport media which both depend on vast network infrastructures. Even if we assume that the train may be the more efficient alternative (think of Japan), it may not prevail (think of the US) because the size of the upfront investment necessary to overcome path dependent advantages of the car. These advantages are continuously reinforced if the road infrastructure is being amended all the time. This is even more the case if in planning new infrastructure existing habits are taken for granted by its designers, such as accepting a preference for cars as a social fact and further cementing (literally) the existing path. This also shows that infrastructure can have transformative impacts on habits if designers adopt other goals: Yet this means that in designing infrastructure they would always need to include how to support the complementary change of habits (Kropp and Sonnberger, 2021). In other words, building new infrastructure means to create a world of new practices (failures are referred to as 'white elephants'). Accordingly, the same applies for building GI wit NbS: This must break existing path dependencies and establish new ones, such as a culture of sustainability (Soini and Dessein, 2016).

The example of the car, as in the shower case, manifests complex co-evolutionary dynamics. The difference is that the transmission of information is not via genes, but via habits, practices, or, most generally, culture. The car is not just a technical artefact, but a cultural icon. Many people have values that strongly undergird the persistence of practices engaging cars. There are massive economic interests of the related industries that try to influence planners' decisions, and so on. Hence, in sum we can analyse path dependencies of automobile technology in terms of co-evolutionary dynamics analogous to niche construction. The infrastructure of automobile society, roads, filling stations, oil exploration, extraction and processing, and so on, is a defining feature of the human niche in modern societies, and the flow of individual actions adapts to it.

Even though this appears to be an entirely artefactual system, we can still count it as natureculture precisely because of the behavioural adaptation on part of the humans. In principle, the infrastructure enables actions with prosthetic functions (in the ANT sense), such that certain artefacts become extensions of the body (Callon, 2008). We

learn to ride bicycles without thinking and use the infrastructure of cycling lanes in cities (Nagatsu et al. 2023). In Vogel's sense, separating culture and nature is misleading in respect of assigning humans themselves to 'non-nature', which is obviously false. Indeed, that seems like separating the termite mound as 'non-nature' from the termites. Following Haff (Haff, 2014c), we also need to consider the reverse connection: The technosphere is essentially dependent on becoming activated and thereby reproduced by human actions, unless it is a structure running completely autonomous once set up (like certain devices sent to outer space).

Another important feature of infrastructure relating to transparency is that its social and political ramifications are often opaque. This applies for both the side of production and use. The political agencies in charge of infrastructure are often technocratic organizations, since infrastructure is technologically complex, hence much of decision making is expert-based and less amenable to wider political participation. On the side of use, infrastructural decisions often have massive social consequences, such as with regard to mobility patterns that enable or constrain access to certain resources and opportunities, such as jobs. Both observations have raised concerns about democratic control and inclusiveness of infrastructure development. However, in the current context we focus on the implication that the salience of the political aspect implies that infrastructure is no longer transparent (Larkin, 2013). Those people who experience disadvantages created by infrastructural design are well aware of its presence. In fact, there are many ways in which infrastructure is political and generates various forms of experiences that are deliberately reflected by various affected groups. For example, infrastructural projects often have special meanings, such as manifesting national or local aspirations to growth and modernization and are seen as such. These meanings may transpire in non-functional design features, such as, in simplest way, just oversize: The four-lane highway in a country where most people cannot afford a car. Even people who are negatively affected by the infrastructure (such as being evicted for sake of its construction) may feel pride about the ambition.

This discussion reveals the political dimension of infrastructure. In considering the politics of infrastructure, the role of aesthetics has been emphasized (Rancière and Engelmann, 2019), which closes the circle in our reasoning about function and

Umwelt. By implication this means that the aesthetics of infrastructure mediates political processes that can also accompany the transition to an eco-centred infrastructural regime which is essential when considering transitions from grey to green infrastructure. We refer to this as ‘sensory governance’ (Schulte-Römer, 2023). Sensory governance refers to a spectrum that includes explicit design of infrastructure by authorities who include aesthetic criteria, to indirect forms of governmentality by which certain politically desired practices emerge, and to co-productive and co-evolutionary forms of endogenously emerging practices that contribute to the realisation of politically aspired goals. In the context of NbS, the politically set goal is socio-ecological transformation for sustainability and resilience, while meeting certain expectations on economic prosperity and social justice.

In concluding our discussion of infrastructure, we situate infrastructure in the conceptual space of co-evolution, co-production and co-creation. This opens the vista on a great variety of types of infrastructure, of which we only identify a few, though essential, examples which illustrate the specific design choices that need to be made. These types differ in the various ways how the ‘co’s’ are manifest in design and operation.

To begin with, grey infrastructure excludes co-creation but allows for co-production, such as citizen participation in the design, which is often a standard in urban planning. Co-production includes the co-evolutionary dimension in the sense that planners cannot fully anticipate the future patterns of practices that relate to the infrastructure, and there are different degrees how far these practices are allowed to deviate from original plans, thus generating a co-evolutionary dynamic, which involves human habits and practices, but excludes other species.

Next, there is a variety of green infrastructure as far as degrees of freedom for co-evolution and co-creation are concerned. There is the borderline case when grey infrastructure is ‘greened’ with full control by the planner including the practice dimension, such as using trees for decorative purposes on public squares. Although this may even be presented as an NbS, co-evolutionary and co-creative aspects are completely missing, and even co-production may not apply, if the greenery is chosen and put into place in a top-down technocratic process. However, the latter can also be

the case when a full scale NbS is implemented, such as creating an urban forest of the Miyawaki type. In this case, the NbS as GI is co-evolutionary and co-creative but lacks co-production. This reveals the potential of conflicts between human and non-human beneficiaries of the green infrastructure.

There is also the possibility that GI may not allow for co-creation, such as wildening, while at the same time keeping leeway for co-evolution, similar to artificial selection on breeding and domestication of other species. Again, these different degrees of maintaining planners' control can combine with different forms of co-production, or even exclude that. There is also the possibility that co-production is excluded, but co-creation is enabled, as in the case of a technocratic scheme to allow for rewildening a place.

All these variants define the space of choices in a field of study and public management that is directly relevant for GI, landscape planning and architecture. So, we turn now to discussing the third of our conceptual triad, landscape.

3.3. Landscape

The notion of landscape has a complex history. Originally, the landscape was directly related to the human viewer, in the sense that it is delimited by the reach and scope of the human view and is qualitatively defined by the aesthetic experience it generates (Carlson, 2020). Hence, a landscape would be a deeply subjective phenomenon. Later, the independent status as nature was more emphasized, only to go along with the innovation of landscape architecture and design, which would translate human aesthetics into building nature, to be distinguished from gardening which would create natural artefacts: A French garden would not be a 'landscape' in this sense. In the course of the 20th century, this resulted in a certain division between the emerging ecological approach to landscape design, which would place less emphasis on the aesthetics, and the architectural approaches which highlight the design aspect and the integration with other built artefacts. Most recently, in the movement of landscape urbanism both aspects are reintegrated (Waldheim, 2016).

To begin with, we take the step to approach landscape as infrastructure (Bélanger, 2009). At first sight, this does not apply to landscapes in the sense of non-built natural

environments, say, a mountain lake viewed by humans. But in the context of tourism, scenic places certainly have the property of infrastructure. This is even more salient in cases such as winter sports, when skiing relies on certain slopes and snow. Following climate change, tourist resorts may invest into built infrastructures of creating artificial slopes with artificial snow. Landscape clearly qualifies as infrastructure for cases such as the coordinated development of green spaces in and around cities. This is 'green infrastructure' (Mell, 2023). The question is whether in this case only the 'green' part counts as landscape or the entire assemblage of grey and green: In the view of landscape urbanism, it is the assemblage (Wieck and Giseke, 2022). Hence, we meet another instance of overcoming the false duality of nature versus artificial, since landscape would no longer be only natural. Yet, following Vogel we might still ask whether there are different degrees in a continuum of variants which are defined by the specific forms of agency involved and the degrees of coevolutionary leeway. The urban park can be tightly controlled by human designers or may be left leeway for spontaneous evolution, as we discussed in previous section.

We suggest conceiving the landscape as the human niche incorporated in a specific habitat. This definition has a normative component as we would not count any kind of habitat as a landscape, despite being part of the human niche. This transpires if we consider the relationship between technosphere and biosphere. A huge harbour such as Rotterdam, despite at the seaside, would not be conceived as landscape, as the harbour marginalizes biospheric processes. An assemblage of large green spaces and buildings counts as landscape. Yet, the harbour is part of the human niche as it plays an important role in accessing resources for human needs. Hence, we can define the landscape as a specific type of assemblage of technospheric and biospheric elements of infrastructure in the human niche.

The notion of landscape directly relates to the concept of *Umwelt*, which highlights the semiotic nature of landscape, in this sense retaining the roots of the notion. This raises the important question whether landscape is necessarily anthropocentric. The ecological approach to landscape architecture reveals an interesting ambivalence here which ties up to our previous discussion of types of infrastructure: In implementing landscape design as engineering GI, this often results in a hierarchical

approach to implementation, both in the sense of being expert-based and realized by technocratic interventions (Whitten, 2023). This has been dubbed ‘green statism’. In practice, this often results in the politicization of building GI, when the proposed design meets local resistance, often driven by aesthetic concerns. Therefore, this motivates a distinction between generic anthropocentrism and embodied and localized anthropocentrism. The former can be fully science-based, and to the contrary, it is this scientific view itself that is anthropocentric. When this view confronts local concerns, this is a clash with embodied anthropocentrism. Yet, as the ongoing discourse about the role of Indigenous knowledge in designing NbS shows, this does not only raise concerns about diverse and possibly conflicting views on landscape design in the local context, but also includes the possibility that some views are themselves non-anthropocentric, such as the case of Australian First people shows (Mata et al., 2020; Povinelli, 2016).

In other words, the notion of landscape includes, firstly, the possibility of local human diversities of perceived landscapes in the same niche, and secondly, leads to the question whether landscape should be conceived as more-than-human (Pollastri et al., 2021). The latter would establish a new view on *Umwelt*, as we suggest conceiving of landscape as the local assemblage of multi-species *Umwelts*. This establishes a parallelism to the concept of niche: The local environment is a set of multi-species niches, and as landscape it is a set of corresponding *Umwelts* (Heras-Escribano and De Pinedo-García, 2018). This difference matters, as we have seen, because the *Umwelt* is the sphere of creative evolution different from the sphere of adaptation and natural selection. We summarize these ideas in figure 15 which further details the framework outlined in figure 8. The human niche remains at the centre, but this niche either offers more-than-human affordances within the niche as utilized by humans, or allows for the emergence of niche assemblages connecting to the human niche.

Figure 15: The extended framework

In the extended framework, the construction of the human niche manifests the two aspects or modes of building infrastructure and landscape. As we have seen, this is a fundamental bimodality in the sense that landscape is infrastructure and infrastructure constitutes landscape. Yet, there are two important differences: First, as we only focus on NbS, we do not consider infrastructure that is mostly ‘built grey’, but there is the catch that this can still become object of other species niche construction, or non-intentional greening from the human viewpoint. Second, the functional aspect of infrastructure tends towards the generic, whereas the *Umwelt* aspect is local. As said, this distinction is often virulent in the clashes between expert- and science-based designs and local communities over NbS. In the multi-species context this leads to the challenge how to recognize the creative potential of other species behaviour beyond established knowledge about ecological functions (Roudavski, 2021).

This challenge suggests approaching landscape and landscape design in terms of multi-species affordances. An obvious example is an urban park. The park embodies a set of affordances for human actions, such as strolling, jogging, or romantic encounters. The park is also brimming with affordances for all other species living at the same place. That means, in designing the park, the human designers may include considering these affordances as well. There are two possible conflicts here.

First, since affordances are aesthetic in the first place, considering non-human affordances may not match with human tastes and preferences (Saito, 2007). In fact, this is also already possible for humans: Often the use of parks is regulated to block the activation of affordances that are embodied, such as, say, prohibiting playing soccer on a lush and spacious lawn. Therefore, we notice that in principle there is no difference between humans and other species, as in both cases human designers may exclude some uses of the park. Apart from direct regulatory force, this can also work via sensory governance, that is the direct design of affordances and the exclusion of some others.

Second, the actions flowing from affordances may directly clash, which includes the case that affordances are discovered that have not been considered in the original design. Parks may attract mobile species that were not living in the neighbourhood previously. Human visitors may feel threatened if only in imagination (Bombieri et al., 2023).

As we see, landscape design as infrastructure is necessarily political, in the sense that there are conflicts and discourses about valuations and actions that search for resolution by various means, reaching from forceful interventions to consensual deliberation. However, given the local nature of the landscape, this can only operate on the corresponding level, which is the community (Hiedanpää and Lovén 2022). Hence, we relate the notion of landscape to the notion of community and approach the community as the pivotal level in NbS design and implementation (Heras-Escribano and De Pinedo-García, 2018). This step relates to approaching the landscape as a 'place' different from the 'space' in which the ecological functions materialize (Tuan, 2011). Accordingly, we can qualify NbS design and implementation as 'placing' an NbS (Gulsrud et al., 2018). This placing includes the perspective of more-than-human extensions of the community, which is an essential condition for including the interests and needs of other species in what remains, after all, human politics.

We summarize our discussion in figure 16: We approach both landscape and community in the more-than-human dimensions, which implies that their relationship is one of co-evolution and co-creation, such as human infrastructure being designed for niche construction by birds, aiming at creating evolutionary potential, while also

recognizing the creative agency of birds in discovering such opportunities, and possibly also contributing to human design activities. This results in a continuous process of niche construction distributed over many forms of agency.

Figure 16: Landscape and community

In the next section, we will explore the practical consequences of our theoretical framework for designing and implementing NbS. We organize this work along five formulae:

- *NbS are ways of placeshaping* for humans and other species, which implies practically that one cannot only consider single NbS but must adopt a holistic approach to landscape design and evolution.
- *NbS are artwork* in terms of activating co-creative development of multi-species affordances directed at evolutionary potential in the future.
- *NbS are practices* engaging many actors, human and other species, in which function and meaning are integrated by specific expressive means, such as rituals.
- *NbS are care* in fostering attitudes of mutual recognition and peaceful co-habitation.

- *NbS are flourishing* in the sense of shared creation of future potentials for self-realization of all members of the more-than-human community, and of maintaining a rich and productive web of interactions.

These formulae translate the abstract notions of co-evolution and co-creation into concepts that allow to conceive NbS as a set of practices.

4. Doing NbS as more-than-human infrastructural landscaping

4.1. Holistic approach

The common theme of the following sections is that NbS should not be approached as single measures but always approached holistically, that is, as an element of a comprehensive local approach to transformation, and that in design and implementation function and meaning must always be considered with equal attention (Tzoulas et al., 2021). Further, the NbS is always conceived as contributing to both human and other species needs and concerns. We interpret doing a specific NBS as contributing to ‘landscaping’ as co-evolutionary human niche building and multi-species niche construction.

Lack of holistic perspectives often results in failures of NbS, often following unintended consequences (Frantzeskaki, 2019; Hobbie and Grimm, 2020). Two most important causes are the failure to upscale and unintended negative consequences. In practice, both failures often relate to economic factors. For example, green gentrification often comes along with NbS such that disadvantaged groups are driven out of an area, even into other areas with worse conditions (Anguelovski et al., 2022). Hence, even though some groups enjoy the advantages of the NbS, in the aggregate, even the functional effects may be negative. Similarly, upscaling may be blocked by budgetary reasons which in turn might relate to differences among the economic position of districts and cities in larger agglomerations. Analogous arguments may apply for other species,

since the complex ecological repercussions of an NbS require to take wider contexts into account (such as migratory species).

Another specification of holism is methodological. It is essential to develop inclusive and integrative criteria of evaluating designs and NbS effects. This applies for the human domain, as in the case of green gentrification, and amounts to a comprehensive stakeholder analysis (Reed et al., 2009). However, in our context the extension to the more-than-human domain deserves more attention as the desiderata are more glaring. The direct way to achieve that is rendering the criterion of biodiversity in terms of the stakeholder notion (Hernandez-Santin et al., 2023). Yet, this does not resolve the tricky question how to 'give voice' to other species stakeholders.

One solution is offered by the practice framework adopted here, which is also familiar from research into humans and their relationship to GI. A standard approach is surveys that, however, presuppose linguistic communication (Sultana et al., 2022). Another one is to approach the green infrastructure as a space of affordances for actions, and to document and analyse such patterns of practices by observation (Mishra et al., 2023). This method easily allows for methodological holism, as the same empirical approach is deployed in ecological repertoire analysis, which also aims at identifying affordances and hence *Umwelts* by observing other species practices (Maran, 2020b). This renders both human and other species practices as objects of investigation within one framework, even to the extent that many activities, seen on an appropriate level of abstraction, can relate to both: For example, a certain location in a park may embody affordances for resting as activity conducted by humans and non-humans alike, such as the human resting on a bench shadowed by a tree and a bird resting on a branch of that tree.

In the following, we pay more attention to the aspects of meaning than to aspects of function, as the latter are better developed in the literature. However, this matches with approaches to technology in the social sciences, but increasingly also in engineering, to conceive technology not merely as an artefact, but as a practice centring on an artefact, and which is embedded into wider frames, summarized as institutions, habits, values and culture (figure 17). This applies for NbS as co-evolutionary technology with full force:

- Institutions relate to the governance of an NbS in local contexts which includes both formal (e.g., budgeting by local government) and informal (such as citizen initiatives) institutions.
- Values relate to embodied stances towards the NbS, such as aesthetic preferences towards nature or moral obligations towards other species.
- Culture refers to all kinds of sense-making practices, such as beliefs about climate change and consequences for the local community, which locate the NbS in cognitive schemes of action.
- Habits are embodied practices that are taken for granted in a local community.

Implementing an NbS by human design means that all these frames are affected and would need to be addressed in theory. This is the principle of holism.

Figure 17: Technology as assemblage (Herrmann-Pillath et al., 2022)

4.2. NBS as ways of placeshaping

The integration of function and meaning is salient in approaching NbS as ways of placeshaping (Horlings et al., 2020). Placeshaping refers to locating the NbS in a comprehensive view of the (urban) landscape and conceptualizing this landscape as meaningful for humans and other species. The place is the medium of forming more-than-human community, which we refer to in section 4.5. as ‘commoning’.

The notion of placeshaping involves a wide range of specific measures and approaches that are familiar from NbS practices (Soini et al., 2023). A most general point is that the NbS is put in the context of the history of the place which is then interpreted in terms of a common destiny of the community. A simple example is urban trees (Gulsrud et al., 2018). One approach to designing urban greenery, parks and forests would be to focus on human aesthetic tastes, or on certain functional criteria, such as the capacities for shadowing and cooling (Vuckovic et al., 2023). Selecting trees as placeshaping would reflect on the history of both the human settlement and of the local ecology. Often, this translates into choosing native species of trees. However, as argued in our theoretical part, these species might not be most adaptable to future conditions of climate change. Since many trees have a lifetime spanning several human generations, choice of trees should be a matter of community concern and can effectively become a medium of community formation. Trees are cultural icons in most, if not all human societies, reaching from animistic beliefs to modern ecological symbolism. Planting and caring for trees can become an important way of placeshaping. This tightly integrates function and meaning, as the concern for tree survival requires thorough consideration of function, while at the same time many activities can make trees meaningful for people, such as in tree planting campaigns, individual tree stewardships and so on.

However, there is also the other species dimension. Trees fulfil a great range of functions for many species, and given climate change, probably new arrangements between tree species and other species need to be found. For example, changing ecological conditions may force certain bird species to find new habitat in urban areas, and for that new spaces for nesting need to be found (Parker et al., 2022a). This can become an occasion for community formation between humans and other species, with humans actively welcoming the new members of the local ecosystem. This example shows that in selecting trees, evolutionary potential is to be considered that inheres the *Umwelt* that is embodied in the tree, that is, the set of affordances (branches for perching, holes for nesting, and so on). In addition, this can include genuinely symbiotic relationships between technospheric and biospheric processes,

when existing trees are equipped with human-made artefacts that support animal activities (Holland et al., 2023).

An important topic in placeshaping is the redevelopment of urban sites that fall into disuse (Teixeira et al., 2021). Modern cities are continuously evolving, especially under the conditions of demographic change and rapid technological transformation. Such projects can become bridges between past and future, where the past may refer to the stage before the area was becoming urban. One important topic is NbS in water management, such as watersheds. Derelict industrial sites can be developed as wetlands, lakes and other forms of water landscapes. This can go along with connecting to the past. In this context, one important example is reinstating meanings that are associated with previous inhabitants of the place, such as, most importantly, First people (Bush et al., 2023). In NbS discourse, often the need is invoked to activate Indigenous knowledge for designing NbS, such as on local plants (Maller, 2021). This can be embedded in community healing of injustice (Country et al., 2016). For example, a formation of rocks and creeks that was overlaid by urban construction may be restored, with both ecological and even engineering function, but also reviving suppressed Indigenous meanings.

Even when it is not possible to restore original conditions, the past can still inform the present. For example, there are urban places which in the past had many waterways that were filled during urban construction. Yet, the design of streets still evokes the past patterns (Almazán and Studiolab Jorge Almazán Architecture Laboratory, 2022). Urban greening can refer to these embodied memories to create a distinct community stance towards the NbS. There are other forms of urban construction that have memorial functions, most obviously cemeteries (Löki et al., 2019), but also historical sites such as gardens (Pękal, 2020). These can become focal points of community activities in NbS, as in relation to trees.

A key point is that such co-creative processes work reciprocally, in the sense that placeshaping itself is more-than-human. That means, in employing co-creation approaches to NbS design other species play an important role in shaping the identity of the human community. This is long familiar from the role of certain key species in communities such as fisherpeople, for example lobster, traditions that extend to the

urban modernity. In recognizing the relationships between such species and the local ecosystem, the human community can become more inclusive to more-than-human beyond iconic species. In fact, all placeshaping is 'naturally' more-than-human: The 'human' often aims at restricting more-than-human placeshaping, such as when eradicating so-called weeds to impose a certain aesthetic pattern in a public park. Plants and animals are active placeshapers in the ecological sense, and human placeshaping can actively, if not pro-actively endorse this more-than-human placeshaping. As we argue in the following section, a key medium of this is artwork that creates affordances for multi-species co-habitation.

A requirement that all this works is that humans establish procedures how to collectively agree on and pursue a shared way of placeshaping. This implies that co-production is an essential element in placeshaping, which requires inclusive institutions and processes of local governance. Placeshaping can be a contentious, if not divisive issue, for example, when a place has different layers of historical depth, such as original Indigenous dwellers versus settler communities, who can be both references for community identities today, and may even relate to different species, similarly distinguishing between original native and newly introduced, though perhaps centuries ago. Such potential cleavages in placeshaping require well-designed approaches to co-production of NbS.

One important part of these is extending existing approaches to stakeholder analysis for humans to other species: For example, the more-than-human landscape view invites to expand stakeholder identification approaches such as based on social identity (Crane and Ruebottom, 2011) towards other species in emphasizing shared identities ('making kin' à la Haraway, 2016). Stakeholder analysis can proceed in a functional way, such as identifying needs, human and more-than human, as in a multi-species understanding of health. Yet, functional analysis cannot help to assess trade-offs, even in the fundamental sense of who will eventually considered to be a stakeholder or not. Hence, stakeholder analysis itself must be co-produced and co-created. This requires transdisciplinary approaches, for example, in relying on methods such as story-telling in identifying concerns and valuations (Stibbe, 2021).

This points to the central role of art in redefining the scientific approach to NbS (Herrmann-Pillath, 2020, IPBES 2022, 377).

4.3. NbS as artwork

The dimension of culture stays in the centre of approaching NbS as artwork. As said, however, this is tightly connected to function as the goal is to enable and motivate creative actions on evolutionary potential: This is well recognized in recent theorizing in urban design that emphasizes the parallelism and synergy between ecology as biology and ecology as urbanism (Corner and Hirsch, 2014; Reed and Lister, 2020). There are two wider topics which count here.

The first is sensory governance of green infrastructure (Schulte-Römer, 2023). The design of a park which has certain functions leaves much leeway for its aesthetics, which is mostly referring to human tastes. These tastes are historically and culturally contingent, but often stay in tension with creating ecological functions for other species (Saito, 2007). A simple example is leaving dead wood on the ground which fulfils a wide range of functions for many species. Even if human uses of the park, such as for jogging, are not affected, for aesthetic reasons this may be removed. Hence, the design of the park is an issue of sensory governance of NbS, and it might not be enough to just explain the function to the human visitors. So, the dead wood may become itself an object of artful design. This is only one example of many where aesthetic tastes of humans may hinder NbS implementation (Frantzeskaki, 2019).

Secondly, and on a deeper level, this points to clashes between human tastes and the aesthetics of other species *Umwelten*. A widespread phenomenon is that what is broken, incomplete, or defunct is rich ground for other species flourishing (Del Tredici, 2014). Think of cracks in the pavement which invite herbaceous plants and in turn insects. Often, human design principles resolutely downgrade such states and invite for action perfecting the artifacts and suppressing the other species. Hence, NbS design needs to define more-than-human aesthetic criteria, such as building on the Japanese principle of wabi-sabi which praises imperfection (Parkes and Loughnane, 2018).

In our previous paper, we introduced the concept of NbS as exaptative art. This means that NbS can create affordances which may not even be known to the human designer, but which are discovered by other species. This can be the imperfect, as said, but also the superfluous, in the sense of the famous ‘spandrels of San Marco’ (Gould and Lewontin, 1979). Modern architecture has mostly eschewed gothic and baroque richness of ornament and other meaningful but functionless elements. In the more-than-human perspective, such richness of functionless elements is a richness of unknown affordances. This can be made operational on various levels, such as on the micro-level level of single architectures or on the meso-level such as leaving urban spaces as open ‘opportunity spaces’ for rewildening (Gomes Sant’Anna, 2023).

However, as we argued in our previous paper, a new NbS aesthetics of exaptation can be informed by generic notions of functions which apply over a wider range of species (Parker et al., 2022c). For example, water is a basic need that has to be met for many purposes, such as drinking or bathing. Modernist architecture often leaves no space for elements that might retain water. So, even the design of the grey built parts of the urban settlement can obtain NbS functions, which is more pronounced when the architecture already takes account of potential for greening walls and roofs in the design stage (Parker et al., 2022b; Weisser et al., 2023).

NbS as artwork is implicit in modern conceptions of ecologically informed landscape architecture and planning. Here the notion of landscape, as suggested in our theoretical part, unfolds in rich variations. One example is the recent trend to recognize landscapes as UNESCO heritage sites, such as the wadden land (Liburd et al., 2021). There are many cultural forms in which landscapes are integral parts of human aesthetic practices, often in a religious setting, such as in Japanese Shinto (Ishizawa, 2018) or Chinese Fengshui (Yu, 2019). Often, the aesthetic experiences have deep historical roots, such as the preservation of long-living oaks in German wetlands, which today have been appropriated as NbS for flood control. So far, such perspectives have mostly been taken in a non-urban context, however, conceptualizing the urban itself as natureculture allows for reinventing the aesthetics of the city (Li and Mell, 2023). This can include new artforms that span the technosphere and the biosphere and enable interspecies art as a part of the urban

fabric, that is, co-creation of art by humans and non-humans mediated by technology such as AI (Ullrich and Trump, 2022).

One elementary form of artwork with wide implications is the role of narratives, with story-telling as one specific form (Stibbe, 2021). The analytical category of narrative does not only include aesthetic practices identified as such, such as nature-writing (Maran, 2020a), but also apparently functional forms, such as the narrative of a local plan to implement an NbS, which establishes a vision of how the NbS is intended to work in the future; even further, scientific accounts themselves often take the form of a narrative, such as in economics (McCloskey, 1998). This has various implications for NbS practice. Story-telling is one of the well-established media of placeshaping and transformative approaches in preparing the ground for initiatives on sustainable development (Pearson et al., 2018). This includes narrative approaches that aim at accessing the 'other worlds' of the more-than human (Despret, 2021). On the one hand, this can be included in the transformative context, but narratives can also have the status of analytical techniques in research that accompanies the transformative process. As said in the previous section, story-telling can be a means to identify the relevant stakeholders in a place, especially in the sense of identifying the relations among them. Such narratives can also become the media of transformation, thus establishing a transdisciplinary framework in which research and researchers are becoming part of the co-creative process (Norström et al., 2020).

4.4. NbS as practices

A key concept in modern urban design is the focus on activities and events, accompanied with the idea that the infrastructure is open to various, even non-intended uses, that is, is evolving through time (Waldheim, 2016). This matches with the general view on NbS developed here, because the NbS cannot be reduced to the material structure in the static sense, such as the trees as such. The NbS is the activities that connect with the structure. We can push this argument further and approach the NbS as practices which include both the human and other species.

This view inhered the previous discussion anyway, as, for example, placeshaping is a form of practice, and artwork incites practices and is a practice of its own status. For

practice theory the distinction between intentional and non-intentional aspects of action is essential, the latter often referred to as 'habitus' (Bourdieu, 2019). This is what transpired in our theoretical discussion: The co-evolution of NbS means evolving habits and non-intentional stances. One example is practices associated with aesthetics: It may be a habitual urge for action to create 'clean' grey spaces in public squares and confine controlled greenery to certain locations.

On a deeper level, practices involve distributed agency, especially when it comes to habitus (Malafouris, 2013). The weed in the pavement crack combines with the human in the practice of weed extraction or poisoning. In this sense, the agency generating the practice is distributed in the assemblage of pavement, cracks, weed and human (classically, Callon, 1986). Corresponding to the notion of practice, we can extend the concept of habitus to the more-than-human (Barua, 2021). This leads back to our generalization of affordances: Landscaping by means of NbS creates assemblages of human and more-than-human affordances which equally relate to human habitus and to other species behavioural stances which therefore qualify as habitus as well. This is salient in cases where the built infrastructure is derelict, as in the vast shantytowns, slums and favelas of the world. For example, street dogs cohabit with the residents of such places, and in the manifold of interactions feral infrastructures are being done, such as street dogs effectively providing security service via the shared habitus of alertness of dogs and people (Barua and Sinha, 2022).

The question is how we can make such insights operational in NbS design. One simple approach is changing habits via rational decisions. This is the systematic reason why NbS design and implementation should be always embedded into community deliberation, since the deliberative process creates the conditions for reflection an ultimately possible change even of habitus, along Deweyan lines: The pros and cons in deliberation make non-intentional drives for action explicit and may thereby foster transformation of habitus. This reinstates the case for co-production.

Another important, though neglected medium of practice is ritual (Bell, 1997). Ritual is a performative practice that does not simply express inner states but is transformative in the sense of creating shared states of the performers, as envisaged in Durkheim's analysis of ritual as medium of community identity. Ritual is also ontologically powerful

in establishing distributed forms of agency between performers and other entities engaged in the ritual. Finally, ritual is an aesthetic practice that engages all senses. Hence, ritual can be an important element of activities such as placeshaping. However, there is also the more fundamental aspect that ritual, as in First people lifeworlds, can establish interactions and communication between humans and other species. Of course, we do not refer here to physical interactions, but to the performative powers of ritual. For example, tree burials are increasingly performed in modern societies without openly subscribing to an animistic ontology; yet, there are ideas about 'becoming a tree' merging with its metabolism (Becher, 2021).

The role of ritual already became salient in the previous section when we referred to certain religious framings of landscapes. But the notion of ritual is by no means limited to the religious domain, as there are many secular rituals, as in consumption, popular music, or sports (Stephenson, 2015). The question is how far secular rituals (Gordon-Lennox, 2017) can become a part of NbS design. Obviously, this might mostly happen via spontaneous creation of rituals in the local communities, such as introducing seasonal festivals centring on the local landscape and the NbS therein. Further, rituals can also be part of everyday life.

One ritual practice shared across cultures is gift-giving. As NbS implicitly invoke reciprocity between humans and non-humans, this can become manifest in rituals of gift-giving. For example, a community garden may approach the neighbourhood for gifts of bio-waste for composting and may later return fresh vegetables at a neighbourhood party celebrating the flow of life in the community, both in the garden and in the community. Another form of gift-giving is the exchange of seeds in communities, which may even become a defining feature of their identities in relation to particular plants, such as trees (Nading and Fisher, 2020). This also applies for more formal arrangements such as community seed banks (Vernooy et al., 2017), as in this case a local public good is created which needs to be sustained in the longer run: Ritual can be a strong medium of commoning such institutions, which we discuss in the next section.

As has been emphasized in the literature, a key aspect of human ritual is its orthopractic nature, allowing for much leeway in actual beliefs, even to the extent that

ritual heals cleavages that might be unsurmountable by discourse (Seligman et al., 2008). This can be extended to the more-than-human, as ritual is a form of behaviour which transcends the human, ritualization being a key theoretical concept in ethology (Stephenson, 2015). Taking the regular walk outdoor is a ritual shared by humans and dogs. That means, ritual can assume a key role for creating shared understanding beyond linguistic communication and beyond anthropomorphic interpretations of other species and provides a fertile ground for developing relationships of care. As such, ritual is a key means of placeshaping, and insofar as the human experience of place is deeply embodied as 'sense of place' (Carolan, 2008; Grenni et al., 2020), embodied more-than-human rituals transcend the limitations of humans being confined to the cage of their language. Yet, ritual also allows for the integration of more-than-human narrative approaches which start out from conventional nature writing, transcending this into experimental literary practice, as we already pointed out in the previous section (Despret, 2021; Middelhoff, 2019; Wheeler, 2016). Human rituals mostly include story-telling as a powerful means to create emotional states such as feelings of bonding and care, in many contexts, such as even business (Massa et al., 2017). This literature can inform NbS in the dimension of managing its implementation (Caspary and Herrmann-Pillath, 2022).

4.5. NbS as care

In the current debate about NbS, justice has become an important theme (Cousins, 2021; Pineda-Pinto et al., 2022). We think that justice must be grounded in the more general attitude of care, since rendering justice to someone presupposes recognizing her needs and aspirations, beyond mere application of certain rational rules and procedure of justice. In legal theory, this refers to equity: Equity results from mutual relationships of care, or Smithian sympathy.

Care does not simply mean recognizing functional needs, since this does not necessarily imply that in case of functional conflict, this is actually 'taken care of'. After all, the weed is going to be eradicated, as it does not deserve care. This difference is often visible in the extreme discrimination between different kinds of living beings in terms of caring: For example, people might express utmost care for pets, but ignore

the plight of pigs in farm factories. The latter may be even justified by human needs for affordable food. Hence, a universalist stance of care must underlie any discourse of justice of NbS.

Such a stance has been systematized as building on five moral principles: Attentiveness, responsibility, competence, responsiveness, and reciprocity: These play a distinct role in the cyclical process of caring, starting with the stage of caring about (paying attention), then followed by caring for (taking responsibility), care giving (having the competence to take care), caring with (enabling the reception of care) and reciprocity (Moriggi et al., 2020). Clearly, the latter is a key aspect in making the more-than-human care work: Caring for nature would also mean that nature takes care of humans, and that humans recognize that. This reciprocity inheres the roles of NbS for human well-being beyond their specific designed function, such as general health benefits (Kadykalo et al., 2019; Marselle et al., 2019; van den Bosch and Ode Sang, 2017).

Caring is a specific form of practice and means that a person takes care of the flourishing of the other. Basically, these can take the forms of protecting and nurturing as practice. Most NbS require continuous tending and caretaking, such as in the case of urban greenery. Caring creates ownership of the NbS, and hence contributes to its sustainability. An institutionalized form of care are stewardships and sponsorships by individuals, institutions such as schools, or neighbourhoods as communities. Caring is a community way of life: For example, there is a fundamental difference between an NbS using goats in forest fire prevention and leave their tending to professionals such as rangers, or establishing a caring relationship to people in the neighbourhood who are the beneficiaries of that 'ecosystem service'. This can become significant for managing goat populations going feral, if the formal system is not economically viable (for example, citizens may attract feral goats by luring them to the place (Pareja et al., 2020).

One important kind of care is nurturing emergent biodiversity in neglected places. Contrary to common perceptions, cities are often brimming with biodiversity, yet precarious (Soanes and Lentini, 2019). Even endangered species may survive in neglected locations. This applies to plants in the first place, but to following up insects

and other animals, too. Caring can be an important factor in upscaling emergent micro-biodiversity (Uchida et al., 2021). In practice, this means to launch activities in the citizen science domain, since resources are too limited to monitor all urban microsites of potential biodiversity. For example, exploring hidden and incipient biodiversity can be a regular part of biology classes at schools, and pupils might become caretakers of certain plants, further exploring their diffusion. There are also activities with wider societal reach, for example neighbourhoods of large spaces such as abandoned airports turned parks where citizens may assume an active role in protecting the area (Jasper, 2020).

We emphasize that caring can be institutionalized, thus becoming also an element in designing NbS governance. One systematic approach is offered by the concept of 'commoning' (Federici and Linebaugh, 2019; Helfrich and Euler, 2021). This builds on Ostrom's theory and practice of commons (Ostrom, 2015), which applies for many NbS as they produce some public good and / or build on common pool goods (Brnkalakova et al. 2022). The example of sheep used for fire prevention is a case in point, as the prevention can be seen as a public good which is co-created by the sheep and the shepherds. The beneficiaries are the human neighbourhoods. Various institutional arrangements can be envisaged that establish compensation mechanisms, as the neighbours have classical incentives to free ride. Hence, one can think of the assemblage of sheep, shepherds and neighbourhoods as a commons. However, often this compensation is managed via the municipality, and there is no relationship between the neighbours and the sheep. Commoning means that this commons is co-created as a community of care between the three parties, shepherds, sheep and neighbours. Different from other formal governance schemes such as taxes and compensations, commoning also changes the relationships between the various actors in terms of habitus, values and emotions, and it is part of placeshaping. For example, the neighbourhoods of a forest may create a social enterprise as a service unit which produces fire prevention, in which not only the shepherds, but also the sheep are recognized as actors, and the various actors take care in the sense of the cycle of care, starting with becoming aware of each other (for example, neighbours may even be not aware of the function of sheep and may see them as a nuisance).

This can be embedded in a wider range of rituals and narratives about fire, sheep and nature at this place.

4.6. NbS as flourishing

Flourishing is a general notion that can be substantiated in many ways, and on the abstract level means fostering evolutionary and developmental potential. In the context of NbS, there are several generic approaches to flourishing.

One common way to assess GI is to evaluate distinct ecosystem services, such as water supply, temperature regulation, or soil conservation, taking as basic hypothesis that ecosystem services of these basic types contribute to both human and non-human flourishing. Different types of NbS have distinct performances, depending on factors such as size, closeness to natural conditions or imperviousness of remaining grey elements (Hanna et al., 2023).

A very important aspect relates to the notions of flow and connectivity, which are principles that apply on many levels and dimensions (Alberti, 2015; Mell, 2023) and are essential for defining a community. In the context of humans, this refers to phenomena of segregation and separation of settlements, such as gated communities versus shantytowns. In an urban community, the ideal state is one of mixing and flowing together, in many forms (Sennett, 2019). Similarly, for the non-human domain, evolutionary potential is bolstered when dense connectivity within the local ecosystem is fostered (LaPoint et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2019). This is an important principle of NbS design with far-reaching consequences: For example, this means that in designing urban greenery, it is necessary to create connections among different parts, such as connecting two parks via a chain of street trees and other greenery or regulating the design of green roofs such that they are an integral part of the local ecosystem. This principle applies on every level, in a fractal fashion, which reveals the utmost importance of community again: On the one pole, it reigns over the design of green infrastructure, on the other pole, the individual choices of greening the balconies of buildings. For example, the reach of insects is limited, and planting certain flowers on balconies may be crucial for expanding the evolutionary flow in the city (Ávila, 2022).

The immediate translation of ‘flourishing’ in doing an NbS is putting biodiversity at the same level of priority as the specific intended function (Filazzola et al., 2019; Friedman, 2021). Although this is generally recognized, it is often ignored in practice, probably for reasons of cost and expediency, and because of the lacking systemic and holistic framework when implementing single measures such as choosing trees for streets (Liu and Slik, 2022) or designing green roofs (Catalano et al., 2018). Further, often established standards, for example, of creating and tending urban parks and forests may not allow for much evolutionary leeway. This is salient when considering radical alternatives such as the Miyawaki forest which is designed for relatively small urban patches but allows for unplanned evolution with constrained human interference (Lewis, 2022). This is another case in point where the aesthetics of NbS becomes crucial: Flourishing is also an aesthetic idea and requires recognition of the many ways of flourishing in the living world.

The previously discussed aspect of exaptative design suggests that we can even employ flourishing on the grey part of infrastructure: The exuberant production of superfluous artefactual elements can be seen as element in a distributed way of flourishing, which eventually means that individual human and non-human creativity interplay in an ecologically productive way. In sum, the ideal of flourishing of NbS is what is commonly conceived as a flourishing landscape as an assemblage of many species and human artefacts.

We summarize this discussion in figure 18. Flourishing refers to the idea of reciprocity between people and nature as fundamental principle of doing NbS as a co-evolutionary technology. This is enabled in the cycle of the five key features that we identified:

Figure 18: NbS as reciprocity in more-than-human flourishing

- *Placeshaping* creates more-than-human landscapes as multi-species niche construction, and the medium of this is
- *Artwork* as co-creating affordances of cohabitation that are manifest in
- *Practices* that are share by humans and other species, and which centre on
- *Care* as the fundamental mode of more-than-human relating that nourishes
- *Flourishing* in the community cohabitating at the landscape continuously cocreated by
- *Placeshaping...*

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